

COMPOUNDS OF CADMIUM BROMIDE AND IODIDE WITH AMINES AND HETEROCYCLIC BASES

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Compounds of cadmium bromide and iodide with primary (mono and di) and secondary amines and heterocyclic bases have been prepared in ethanol, their properties studied and structures discussed.

Compounds of cadmium halides with urea (Neubauer and Kerner, *Annalen*, 1875, 101, 337), with 3:5-dibromo-*o*-toluidine (Hann and Spencer, *J. Wash. Acad. Sci.*, 1925, 15, 163), with ethylenediamine (Grossmann and Schück, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1906, 50, 21), with chloro- and bromoquinolines (Mikailenko, *J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 61, 2253), with *o*-phenylenediamine and *o*-toluylenediamine (Wahl, Forh III Nord. Kemistnotete, 1928, pp. 172-176) and with dodecylamine (Broome *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 67) have been previously reported in literature.

The present investigation was undertaken with a view to studying the formation of the compounds of $CdBr_2$ and CdI_2 with amines and heterocyclic bases in absolute ethanol medium.

EXPERIMENTAL

The amines, heterocyclic bases, $CdBr_2$ and CdI_2 used were of Merck's or B.D.H. 'extra pure' quality. Ethanol was distilled over lime and redistilled over anhydrous copper sulphate.

An ethanolic solution of the amine or heterocyclic base was added to $CdBr_2$ or CdI_2 solution in ethanol with constant stirring till the precipitation was complete. The precipitate was filtered, and washed with absolute alcohol till the washings did not form any precipitate with the corresponding cadmium halide solution. It was dried at about 100° in an air-oven, analysed and properties studied.

Bromine or iodine was estimated by Piria and Schiff's method, and cadmium as cadmium sulphate. Nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl's method in a few cases, and for the rest, it was obtained by difference. In the case of compounds of $CdBr_2$ with primary monoamines and secondary amines, the amine was estimated potentiometrically by bromate-bromide mixture and the percentage of nitrogen in the compound calculated.

TABLE I

Compounds of cadmium iodide with primary mono- and diamines.

Amine.	Compound formed.	M.P.	% Cadmium.		% Iodine.		% Amine.	
			Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1. Aniline	$Cd(C_6H_5NH_2)_2 I_2$	182°	20.17	20.35	45.81	45.96	34.02	33.69
2. α -Naphthylamine	$Cd(C_{10}H_7NH_2)_2 I_2$	207°	17.36	17.23	39.20	38.90	43.44	43.67
3. β -Naphthylamine	Do	196°	17.10	17.23	38.82	38.90	44.08	43.87
4. <i>o</i> -Toluidine	$Cd(CH_3.C_6H_4.NH_2)_2 I_2$	167°	19.29	19.36	43.48	43.73	37.23	36.91
5. <i>m</i> -Toluidine	Do	178°	19.23	19.36	43.46	43.73	37.15	36.91
6. <i>p</i> -Toluidine	Do	184°	19.22	19.36	43.60	43.73	37.18	36.91
7. Benzylamine	$Cd(C_6H_5.CH_2NH_2)_2 I_2$	Decompose before melting	19.45	19.36	43.60	43.73	36.95	36.91
8. Benzidine	$Cd(NH_2.C_6H_4.C_6H_4.NH_2)_2 I_2$	Do	20.37	20.42	45.78	46.13	33.85	33.45
9. <i>p</i> -Phenylenediamine	$Cd \{ C_6H_4(NH_2)_2 \}_2 I_2$	Do	23.48	23.69	53.22	53.51	23.30	22.80

TABLE II

Compounds of cadmium bromide with amines and heterocyclic bases.

Amine or heterocyclic bases.	Compound formed.	% Cadmium.		% Bromine.		% Nitrogen.	
		Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1. Aniline	$\text{Cd}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2)_2 \text{Br}_2$	24.50	24.56	34.81	34.87	6.098	6.108
2. α -Naphthylamine	$\text{Cd}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{NH}_2)_2 \text{Br}_2$	20.17	20.14	28.48	28.63	5.041	5.017
3. β -Naphthylamine	Do	20.09	20.14	28.60	28.63	4.992	5.017
o-Toluidine	$\text{Cd}(\text{CH}_3\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-NH}_2)_2 \text{Br}_2$	23.03	23.13	32.63	32.87	5.742	5.757
o-Toluidine	Do	23.09	23.13	32.76	32.87	5.740	5.757
6. p-Toluidine	Do	23.21	23.13	32.69	32.87	5.776	5.757
7. o-Anisidine	$\text{Cd}(\text{CH}_3\text{O-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-NH}_2)_2 \text{Br}_2$	21.85	21.69	30.67	30.84	5.364	5.403
8. p-Anisidine	Do	21.81	21.69	30.73	30.84	5.388	5.403
9. o-Phenetidine	$\text{Cd}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{O-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-NH}_2)_2 \text{Br}_2$	20.47	20.57	29.09	29.25	5.109	5.128
10. p-Phenetidine	Do	20.71	20.57	29.21	29.25	5.117	5.128
11. Benzylamine	$\text{Cd}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-CH}_2\text{-NH}_2)_2 \text{Br}_2$	23.24	23.12	32.75	32.87	5.751	5.759
12. Benzidine	$\text{Cd}(\text{NH}_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-NH}_2)_2 \text{Br}_2$	24.89	24.63	34.99	35.01	6.081	6.141
13. o-Tolidine	$\text{Cd}(\text{CH}_3\text{-NH}_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_3\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-NH}_2\text{-CH}_3)_2 \text{Br}_2$	23.37	23.21	32.86	33.01	5.722	5.784
14. m-Phenylenediamine	$\text{Cd} \left\{ \text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{NH}_2)_2 \right\}_2 \text{Br}_2$	29.77	29.56	41.94	42.03	7.310	7.365
15. p-Phenylenediamine	Do	29.59	29.56	41.96	42.03	7.293	7.365
16. o-Dianisidine	$\text{Cd}(\text{CH}_3\text{O-NH}_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-C}_6\text{H}_3\text{-NH}_2\text{-OCH}_3)_2 \text{Br}_2$	21.85	21.77	30.91	30.96	5.392	5.425
17. Phenylhydrazine	$\text{Cd}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NH-NH}_2)_2 \text{Br}_2$	29.68	29.56	41.89	42.03	7.324	7.365
18. Ethylaniline	$\text{Cd}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-NHC}_2\text{H}_5)_2 \text{Br}_2$	21.83	21.85	30.96	31.08	5.495	5.445
19. Benzylaniline	$\text{Cd}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-NHC}_6\text{H}_5)_2 \text{Br}_2$	18.49	18.42	26.12	26.19	5.555	5.588
20. Pyridine	$\text{Cd}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N})_2 \text{Br}_2$	26.20	26.12	37.31	37.15	6.468	6.509
21. α -Picoline	$\text{Cd}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{N})_2 \text{Br}_2$	24.54	24.56	34.78	34.87	6.124	6.108
22. γ -Picoline	Do	24.68	24.56	34.81	34.87	6.098	6.108
23. Piperidine	$\text{Cd}(\text{C}_4\text{H}_{11}\text{N})_2 \text{Br}_2$	25.59	25.42	35.99	36.14	6.327	6.333
24. Quinoline	$\text{Cd}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N})_2 \text{Br}_2$	21.40	21.19	29.95	30.14	5.278	5.281
25. Piperazine	$\text{Cd}(\text{C}_4\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2)_2 \text{Br}_2$	31.41	31.37	44.41	44.61	7.872	7.816

DISCUSSION

All the compounds are stable at the room temperature but decompose when treated with strong acids. Excepting the compounds formed with benzidine and o-tolidine, all the rest dissolve in H_2SO_4 (dilute). These decompose into the corresponding amine, sodium bromide and cadmium hydroxide when treated with NaOH (dilute).

The compounds formed with diamines are comparatively stable and hydrolyse slowly even on boiling with dilute alkali solution. All these compounds are insoluble in ethanol, benzene and acetone. The compounds formed with primary monoamines are, however, sparingly soluble in acetone.

The compounds of CdBr_2 with amines and heterocyclic bases are stable towards heat up to 300° , but decompose above that temperature before melting. The compounds of CdBr_2 with α - and β -naphthylamines decompose above 200° before melting. When heated with sodalime, the corresponding amine or heterocyclic base separates out and condenses on the cooler parts of the test tube.

In all the cases studied, two molecules of a monoamine or a heterocyclic base and one molecule of a diamine attach themselves to one molecule of CdBr_2 or CdI_2 . The E.A.N. of cadmium assumes inert gas configuration and the compounds are fairly stable.

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